

Short name	Accounting/reporting of storage and leakage	Long name	Missing or inadequate accounting/reporting practices at the national level
Geographical scope	National level, issue identified in region X		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Whenever a new type of capture, transport or storage process is first piloted, staff tasked with updating the national GHG inventory may not be aware of- or lack guidance for how to report these mitigation activities.</p> <p>For some types of CCU or CCS value-chains GHG inventory guidance may even be entirely missing.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Direct air capture does not unambiguously fit any existing GHG inventory reporting (sub-)sector-category. Category <i>2.H.3. Other.</i> may be appropriate, however ¹ .		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accounting readiness - Accounting of DAC - Accounting of BECCS - Project specific monitoring reporting and verification practices 		

¹ This suggestion has been discussed as a possible resolution, which appears fully in line with GHG inventory guidance, but – to the authors' knowledge is not yet established common practice.